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Data Leakage Detection Algorithm based on Task Sequences and Probabilities

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Abstract. In this paper we propose a novel algorithm to detect anomalous user behaviour in computer sessions. We first identify the behavioural profile of each authorized user from the computational tasks they usually carry out on the files of the information system. A new session is then codified as 2-length sequences and an algorithm based on the probability of those sequences is applied. The activities classified as possible anomalies are double-checked by applying Markov chains. The procedure has been proved efficient in terms of high detection accuracy and low false positive rate. It has been validate on a real database provided by a governmental institution of Ecuador and also on a public dataset of Unix commands. Besides, the algorithm has been shown efficient regarding computational time and the overhead of this monitoring software is low.

Keywords: Anomaly detection, Computer user behaviour, Markov chains, Data leakage, Knowledge-based decision system.

1. Introduction

Data Leakage (DL) is a serious and increasingly common problem for organizations, companies and institutions around the world. This problem can be defined as the unauthorized transfer of classified information from a computer or data centre to the outside world. That is, theft of computer based sensitive information. Sensitive data in companies and organizations include intellectual property, financial information, patient information, personal credit-card data, and any other information depending on the business and the industry involved (Lewellen et al., 2012; Huth et al. 2013).

The study presented in Cisco (2008) reveals that organizations experienced about one threat per month. A significant proportion of computer and organizational security professionals believe insider threat is the greatest risk to their enterprise. Even more, internal fraud produces bigger financial losses in comparison to

intrusions from outside the organization. These types of incidents, whether caused by malicious intent or an inadvertent mistake, can diminish a company's brand, reduce shareholder value, and damage the company's or organization goodwill and reputation (Shabtai, Elovici, and Rokach, 2012). But preventing theft by employees

Being in this situation, the utility and necessity of any system that helps to alleviate this problem is more than justified. Therefore, the major goal of this paper is, on the one hand, to draw attention to this specific problem and, on the other hand, to propose an efficient knowledge-based algorithm for countering data leakage that, besides, reduces the number of false positives, which is the crucial problem of the data leakage detection methods. It is based on the user behaviour when working on a computational information system. The procedure is as follows. First we do anomaly detection, particularly, the algorithm we propose deals with the probability of sequences of operations performed by an authorized user on a workstation. If the output of the algorithm is that the actions carried out by the user corresponds to the expected ones, those sequences are identified as normal and removed from the system. Only sequences that are classified as possible anomaly by this algorithm are then evaluated using Markov chains, to double-check it. In case the information the user is working with is confidential or critical, we may then consider it a data leakage. The system has been proved reliable and efficient, with a low false positive rate.

Our work differs from existing research in the way we deal with the information about the computational operations of each user. We have developed a dynamic structure to codify the operations of the user in a computer system. This has allowed us to extract a user profile that can be obtained by the sequences of actions performed by the user from the historical database. We take into account not only the actions/commands or their relative frequency but the sequence of these operations, which gives us more relevant information and allows us to better detect this type of attacks.

This decision-making system has been validated on real data from a governmental institution of Equator with satisfactory results, and compared to another anomaly detection algorithm on a different public dataset, where it has been also applied, showing its potential adaptation to broader real-world application.

Another advantage of this detection system is that, once it has been trained, it can be applied on-line. The algorithm is able to analyse a sequence of operations within the current working session and, moreover, the users do not realize that they are being monitored as the overhead of the system is very low.

This rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 summarizes related work on the topic of data leakage prevention and data leakage detection. In section 3, the problem is described and the materials (dataset) and methods used are presented. Section 4 details the development of the data leakage detection algorithm and its application. Results are discussed in section 5. The paper ends with the conclusions.

2. Background and related works

Data stored on the corporate networks is at risk because it is more accessible than ever. Organizations provide easy access to databases for information sharing, and storage and compression technology has allowed for more powerful (and risk-laden) operations. This increases the risk of confidential information falling into unauthorized hands. Information/Data Leakage poses a serious threat to companies and organizations, as the number of leakage incidents and the cost they inflict continues to increase.

We are assuming that whether caused by malicious intent (Chatziadam et al., 2014), or an inadvertent mistake, by an insider or outsider (Liao et al., 2013), in any case, sensitive information lost can seriously hurt an organization. To reduce data leakage, two approaches have been proposed: Data Leak Prevention (DLP) and Data Leak Detection (DLD). Our work falls in the second category.

2.1 Data Leak Prevention

Data leakage prevention (DLP) has been studied both in academic research areas and in practical application domains. DLP is a suite of technologies aimed at safeguarding the computing resources to prevent leakage of confidential information found on hard drives, databases, etc. It focuses on the location, classification and monitoring of information at rest, in use and in motion. This solution can go far in helping in stopping the numerous leaks of information that occur each day on the globe.

DLP solutions can be classified according to various aspects such as: leakage source, data state, leakage channel, deployment scheme, preventive/detective approaches, and the action upon leakage (Shabtai, Elovici, and Rokach, 2012). In short, DLP techniques consist of detecting sensitive information that maybe altered in anyway.

Most DLP tools have been installed at the front ends and are called agents. They use the operative system or other PC resources to scan the user activities. The agents identify sensitive information (e.g. credit card numbers, social security codes, etc.) by content - regardless of whether it is data in process of being transmitted over the network (data in motion, DIM), data on a server (data at rest, DAR), or data at an endpoint like a PC (data in use, DIU). Then these DLP proceed to encrypt or to block it (Modi et al., 2013). But the information should be monitored more efficiently to reduce data loss statistics (Ghorbanian, Fryklund, and Axelsson, 2015).

A major problem with DLP is that they rarely consider the flow of specified sensitive data items through the system in their decision process, but most often rely on the on-the-fly identification of sensitive data by using pattern matching or statistical algorithms. Besides, DLP techniques are often limited in terms of flexibility due to security policies established by governments and institutions.

As an example of the rates of detection that some developed tools can provide, in the work by Eesa, Orman, and Brifcani (2015), the authors apply the cuttlefish algorithm to select some features on the KDD Cup 99 dataset and obtain a high detection (92.83% correctly classified) and accuracy (92.051%) rates with a low false alarm rate (1.41%). The false positive rate was high (5.3%) in Yeung and Ding (2003), and in Chari and Cheng (2003) (5%), with static behavioural models and rules (policies) for regulating access to system resources. The detection rate is good but not so high in other works such as the one by Liu and Lai (2009), 80%, and Ye et al. (2002), with 90%.

In summary, it is difficult to identify sensitive information and prevent leaking and, at the same time, ensuring the authorized users access to this information.

2.2 Data Leakage Detection

Incidents of data leakage in which personal or commercial sensitive data is leaked to untrusted or non-intended recipients are on the rise. Although researches on data leakage prevention are emerging, there is little research on the detection of information leakage from the perspective of user behaviour (Xu et al.,

2014). This is due to the fact that when detection is based on user behavioural patterns the problem becomes more complex. It requires, somehow, modelling the "normal" behaviour of authorized users. This can produce a high number of false positives because of the similarity between the expected behaviour of the authorized user that has to perform many different tasks or attempts to leak information. The efficiency of these systems is sometimes questionable (Kumar et al., 2013).

These strategies consist of monitoring users rather than the information itself. That is, it is not based on alterations of the stored data but identifying the perpetrator (Kim and Kim, 2010; Vavilis et al. 2015). Examples of intrusion detection systems can be found in (Chavan and Desai, 2013) and Papadimitriou and Garcia-Molina (2011). In Kamra, Terzi, and Bertino (2008), a mining process is used to form profiles that can model normal database access behaviour and identify intruders, based on the role of the employees. These methods usually estimate the likelihood of leakage and send an alert. In Mathew et al. (2010) authors model users' access patterns by profiling the data points that users access, regarding query syntax. They apply statistical learning algorithms. Ye and Chen (2001) present an anomaly detection technique based on a chi-square statistic. This technique builds a profile of normal events in an information system and detects anomalies.

But many pattern recognition techniques and clustering strategies can be applied to obtain the dynamic profile of user's behaviour (Torgo and Lopes, 2011; Ahmed, Mahmood, and Islam, 2016; Aziz, Sanaa, and Hassani, 2016). Even more, no single technique can provide efficient intrusion detection (Sivakami, Jaiganesh and Saravanan, 2017). An example of the application of different techniques to this very same dataset can be found in (Guevara et al. 2016a), where Negative Selection and the Knuth Morris Pratt Algorithm are used. In that case many more data were used, most of them synthetically generated from the historical behaviour of the user in order to increase the number of negative samples of sequences. Similar results can be seen in (Guevara et al., 2014b), where sub-sequences are generated from normal ones and the system is trained with those sequences. In that paper Bayes Networks and the Page Rank algorithm were applied. In Guevara et al. (2016b), a combination of neural networks and decision trees were applied to identify users and detect intrusions on the same database we are working here, with encouraging results.

Most of the papers that address similar problems deal with relative frequencies or other static characteristics of the information instead of sequence of activities. A notable exception is found in (Costante et al. 2013), where authors monitor database activities and present a framework that automatically learns normal user behaviour, in terms of database activities, and detects anomalies as deviation from such behaviour.

We will compare our work with the one by Aeberhard et al. (1994), who used a Unix command dataset. From it we have extracted the sequences of commands of different users and apply our algorithm to them. Results on this public real database are shown in Section 5 of this paper. Authors apply eight classifiers and their best result in terms of accuracy is 70.5% while ours gives 91.51%.

Our work applies anomaly detection but aiming at particularly reducing the number of false alarms, which is one of the main drawbacks of the detection methods.

3. Materials and Methods

This study deals with authorized users who are allowed to access the computer information system (Figure 1). It is assumed that some kind of intrusion detection system (IDS) has been previously applied. But once

the user has login into the system, it is difficult to identify whether he/she is performing regular tasks or trying to leak information. Daily tasks can include sending out sensitive information.

Figure 1: Research area: data leakage detection.

Some of the difficulties come from the fact that the same user can present very different behaviour depending on the tasks he is in charge of at that moment. Only regarding the number of operations carried out by a user, the profile changes every month (Figure 2), or it even varies during the same period of time but in different years (Figure 3). This situation is even more different for the same user if we take into account the type of operation, the file he is working with, etc.

Figure 2. Behaviour of users #18 (left) and #6 (right) in April (solid blue) and May (dotted red).

Figure 3. Behaviour of users #18 (left) and #6 (right) the same month (May) in 2011(solid blue), 2012 (dotted red), 2013 (dotted green).

Because of that, the high ratio of false alarms that it is usually obtained by the data leakage detection systems is one of the main issues.

3.1 Dataset representation

The first step to approach the modelling of user behaviour is to use a flexible and efficient data structure. This representation must allow dynamic changes at least in the length of the registers or users (Wu and Yen, 2009).

In this work real data are provided (and anonymized) by a governmental institution of Ecuador. The database includes the tasks performed by 22 authorized users on different computers that belong to the institution. All of them had access to the same information resources. Only 10 of them stayed in the same institution the period of time we were interested in, from 2011 to 2013. Each user had an access profile that allowed him to execute only certain operations on specific files according to the position in the institution. The total number of access (computer sessions) over those three years was 12.727 and, since in each session several operation were executed, the number of operations registered those years is 573.731.

Among the characteristics of each access, the attributes that provide the most significant information about the behaviour of the agents are selected (Guevara et al., 2014a). They are listed in the following tables.

Access Table (Login)

This access table contains users' login information. Users U_i are authorized people that work with the computer system, and a set of users is defined as $U = \{U_1, U_2, \dots, U_m\}$, where in our case $m = 10$. Among others, this table contains the attributes *day*, *hour* and *minute*, which describes when the user logs into the system each time, and the duration of each session.

Tasks Table

This table represents the activities carried out by the users into the computer system. The operations (OP_i) the user can perform with the files are: OP_1 =Update, OP_2 =Delete, OP_3 =Insert and OP_4 =Find. They work on 7 repositories or databases, R_j , each of them with different files which contain information about state properties, financial data, etc. Some of the repositories are considered to have confidential information.

A task T_n is defined as an operation OP_i executed on a repository, R_j , i.e. $T_n = (OP_i, R_j)$. We have considered a limited number of possible tasks, in this case 28 tasks (4 operations on 7 databases). The set of tasks executed by a user U_i is represented as $T^{U_i} = \{T_1^{U_i}, T_2^{U_i}, T_3^{U_i}, \dots, T_k^{U_i}\}$.

Figure 4. Data structure of the tasks performed by a user U in a computer system.

The information of the tasks carried out by the users is codified and unified as shown in Figure 4 (User Behaviour Table). The database of tasks is sorted according to the day, hour and minute that every task was executed by each user U_i . In this way, it is possible to determine the sequence of tasks $T_k^{U_i}$ in a session and codified it to obtain a pattern. Sequence refers to a list of two linked task within a session, denoted as $sq(T_i, T_j)$ or (i, j) .

For instance, Figure 5 shows the database that is generated for a specific user, let us say U_1 . Each row corresponds to a computer session, $s_i^{U_1}$. A session is a series of tasks executed by the user. The set of sessions each user has carried out is stored (historical database) and called Passive Session (S^{U_i}). It represents the historical behavior of the user, $S^{U_i} = \{s_1^{U_i}, s_2^{U_i}, \dots, s_p^{U_i}\}$. In this example, user 1 has login the system six times ($p = 6$).

The length of a session depends on the number of tasks the user executes each time. For example, the first row represents $S_1^{U_1}$ and it consists of 6 tasks whereas the length of session 4th (fourth row) is 4. Any new session of the user, called Active Session, $s_{act}^{U_i}$ (Figure 5, bottom), will be compared to the pattern obtained for that user, to determine if it corresponds to the expected behaviour of that user regarding the operation, files accessed, time, etc., or it could be a leakage.

Figure 5. Database of user sessions.

3.2 Methods

In this paper, we have developed a novel algorithm to detect anomalous user behaviour in computer systems. It goes through a series of steps in order to double-check the identification of a leakage and to reduce the number of false alarms. Besides the calculation of some statistical characteristics and the likelihood of a sequence of commands, we finally apply Markov chains to make a final decision.

Markov chain is a random process that undergoes transitions from one state A to state B on a state space. The probability distribution of the state B depends only on the current state A and not on the sequence of previous events (Kemeny and Snell, 1960).

The formulation of this procedure is as follows, where the states are tasks in our case. Given a set of states $T = \{T_1, T_2, T_3, \dots, T_m\}$, the probability of the transition between two of them in one step is defined as a_{ij} , i.e., the probability that the system switches from T_i to T_j is:

$$a_{ij} = Pr(T_m = j | T_1 = t_1, T_2 = t_2, \dots, T_{(m-1)} = i)$$

$$a_{ij} = Pr(T_m = j / T_{(m-1)} = i) \quad (1)$$

The probability of going from state i to state j in m time steps is $P_{ij}^{(m)} = Pr(T_m = j / T_0 = i)$, and the single-step transition is $P_{ij} = Pr(T_1 = j / T_0 = i)$. In general, for a time-homogeneous Markov chain the transition matrix is:

$$P_{ij}^{(m)} = Pr(T_{(k+m)} = j / T_k = i) \quad (2)$$

and

$$P_{ij} = Pr(T_{(k+1)} = j / T_k = i) \quad (3)$$

The m -step transition probabilities satisfy the Chapman-Kolmogorov equation, $P_{ij}^{(m)} = \sum_{r \in S} P_{ir}^{(k)} * P_{rj}^{(n-k)}$, $0 < k < m$, where S is the state space of the Markov chain. Let X_k be the marginal random variable that sets the state at step k , then X_0 sets for the initial step.

$$P(X_k = j) = \sum_{r \in S} P_{rj}^k * P(X_0 = r) \quad (4)$$

Markov chains have many applications as statistical models of real-world processes, particularly, in the field of intrusion detection (Nadeem and Howarth, 2013), anomaly detection (Sha et al., 2013), etc.

4. Data leakage detection algorithm based on sequences of tasks

As it was said in the introduction, first we apply anomaly detection and then do data leakage. The detection algorithm we propose consists of several steps in order to double check the final decision on whether it is an attempted attack or not. The steps of this algorithm are the following:

- Step 1: Calculation of sequence probability based on historical data.
- Step 2: Calculation of the more and less likely sequences within a session.
- Step 3: Checking anomalous sequences using Markov Chains.

4.1 Step 1: Calculation of sequence probability based on historical data

In this step, the algorithm uses information from the historical database of tasks to identify all 2-length sequences of tasks (T_i, T_j) of a specific user and generates his profile.

The probability matrix of the sequences, $P_{sq}(i, j)$, for user U_x , is calculated as,

$$P_{sq}^{U_x}(i, j) = \frac{Q_{ij}^{U_x}}{\sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^m Q_{ij}^{U_x}} \quad (5)$$

Where each element $Q_{ij}^{U_x}$ of the square matrix is the number of times the sequence (T_i, T_j) has been executed by user U_x . Note that $sq(T_i, T_j) \neq sq(T_j, T_i)$.

In the $P_{sq}(i, j)$ matrix, the sequences (i, j) are classified into two groups: the most (+) and less (-) likely sequences. The sequence with highest probability defines the P_{Max} value and the sequence with the smallest probability gives the P_{Min} value. A threshold, $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, is defined as the mean of these values, $\alpha = (P_{Max} + P_{Min})/2$.

A threshold for anomaly detection is defined as a value that classifies the actions of a specific user into two classes: anomalous and expected or normal ones, depending of the relative frequency the user carries out those actions. According to the each system one could choose a different threshold. In this work the thresholds are not fixed in advance as they are a function of the probabilities of the real sequences of the users. In this particular case, taking the mean of those probabilities to implement this threshold gave us good values while keeping it simple.

Let us see an example. For user U_1 , according to Figure 5, Q_{11} is the number of times the sequence of task (T_1, T_1) appears in that user's historical database. In this case is 1 (see Figure 5, fourth row, $s_4^{U_1}$). The rest of the values of Q_{ij} are calculated the same way. For instance, $(T_1, T_2) = 3$, $(T_2, T_1) = 2$, and so on. Therefore, the matrix Q_{ij} for user U_1 , with $k = 4$, is:

$$Q_{ij}^{U_1} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 3 & 2 & 0 \\ 2 & 0 & 1 & 3 \\ 1 & 2 & 1 & 1 \\ 2 & 0 & 2 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

As the probability matrix $P_{sq}^{U_1}(i, j)$ uses the sum of times any sequence appears in the U_1 database, in this case $\sum_i \sum_j Q_{ij} = 22$. Therefore, $P_{sq}^{U_1}(i, j) = Q_{ij}/22$. The threshold is then $\alpha = 0.068$ because $P_{max} = 3/22$ and $P_{min} = 0$. Finally,

$$P_{sq}(i, j) = \begin{bmatrix} 0.045 & 0.136 & 0.090 & 0 \\ 0.090 & 0 & 0.045 & 0.136 \\ 0.045 & 0.090 & 0.045 & 0.045 \\ 0.090 & 0 & 0.090 & 0.045 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} - & + & + & - \\ + & - & - & + \\ - & + & - & - \\ + & - & + & - \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

4.2 Step 2: Calculation of the more and less likely sequences within a session

In this step the algorithm calculates the percentage of 2-length sequences (T_i, T_j) labelled as (+) and (-) for each session. This percentage is called Mp_{S_k} and Lp_{S_k} , respectively, where S_k is the session that is being evaluated, which belongs to the set of historical sessions S^{U_x} . That is,

$$Mp_{S_k} = \frac{\sum Psq_i(+)}{|S_k|-1} 100\%, \quad Lp_{S_k} = \frac{\sum Psq_i(-)}{|S_k|-1} 100\% \quad (8)$$

The numerator is the number of sequences (+) or (-) in S_k and the denominator is the number of 2-length sequences within S_k (number of task minus 1).

Figure 6 shows the values for user U_1 and Table 1 the corresponding indexes.

Figure 6. More and less likely sequences in the user database.

Table 1. Percentage of more and less likely sequences for user U_1 .

S_i	Nº sq	Nº of (+)	Mp_{S_i}	Nº of (-)	Lp_{S_i}
1	5	2	40%	3	60%
2	4	4	100%	0	0%
3	5	4	80%	1	20%

4	3	2	66.66%	1	33.33%
5	2	2	100%	0	0%
6	3	2	66.66%	1	33.33%

The minimum of each of these indexes will be set as other thresholds, that is, Mp_{min} and Lp_{min} . In the example (Table 1), $Mp_{min} = 0.4$ and $Lp_{min} = 0$.

Once these thresholds have been obtained, they are applied to any new session of the user. Following the notation, for the actual session of U_1 (Figure 6, last row):

$$Mp_{sact} = \frac{\sum Psq_i(+)}{|S_{act}|-1} 100\% = \frac{2}{4} \times 100\%,$$

$$Lp_{sact} = \frac{\sum Psq_i(-)}{|S_{act}|-1} 100\% = \frac{2}{4} \times 100\%.$$

Where the length of the session is 5 (number of tasks of that session).

Based on these indexes, it is possible to determine if so far the activity of the user can be considered an attempt of data leakage (if the indexes surpass the threshold). If so, we will continue the procedure to be sure of it. Otherwise it is not an anomaly and therefore this user activity is classified as normal.

In the example, $Mp_{sact} = 50\% \geq Mp_{min}$ and $Lp_{sact} = 50\% \geq 0\%$. The result of this step is true, meaning the decision is not clear since it could be an anomalous activity. Using a conservative policy we would identify it as a possible attack and generate an alarm. But if it is not, we would be generating false alarms and hindering the normal operation of the system.

Therefore we will try to improve these results by applying another technique, the Markov chain, to double-check this result.

4.3 Step 3: Checking anomalous sequence using Markov Chains.

Once the step 2 of the algorithm has been evaluated, we obtain a first decision on the behaviour of the user (normal or possible attack). If the result is normal (expected behaviour), we do not need to continue with the procedure and the system identifies those actions as corresponding to that authorized user. Otherwise, if the result of step 2 is that the user still has some probability of being trying to leakage information, in order to validate this statement we go on with step 3. This way, we get a second “opinion” on the user behaviour, and then the number of false positive can be reduced. It is worthy to remark that Markov chains are only applied to the possible anomalous sequences that result from step 2.

On the other hand, we have evaluated the results before and after applying the Markov chains to show the utility of this double-checking. This last step is just a verification of whether a probably anomalous action is a real attempted attack. Therefore, the Markov chains add extra information about the probability of being an attack. Indeed, as it will be shown, when we apply the Markov chain the number of false positive decreases and therefore, the accuracy of the classifier improves.

The Markov chains are applied to determine two types of anomalies:

- Anomaly detection type A: anomalies of 2-length sequences (T_i, T_j) within $S_{act}^{U_i}$ in one step.
- Anomaly detection type B: anomalies of 2-length sequences (T_i, T_j) within $S_{act}^{U_i}$ in m steps.

4.3.1 Anomaly detection type A

Let U_x be a user and T_i, T_j two tasks that belong to the set of tasks $\{T_1 \dots T_m\}$. The set $\Omega_i^{U_x} = \{(T_1, T_i) \dots (T_m, T_i)\}$ ($i=1 \dots m$) is the sample space of the activities performed by user U_x . The event $(T_i, T_j) \in \Omega_i^{U_x}$ means the user executes the sequence of tasks T_i-T_j . Normal activity of a user is related to frequent events and anomalous actions are linked to infrequent sequences of activities. In this sense, we can define the single step transition matrix (equation 3), $P = (p_{ij})_{i,j=1 \dots m}$, as the relative frequency matrix obtained from historical data of user U_x , where p_{ij} is an estimation of the probability of user U_x going from task i to task j in one step.

Each element of matrix P is calculated by applying the Laplace rule, $p_{ij} = \frac{Q_{ij}^{U_x}}{\sum_{s=1}^m Q_{is}^{U_x}}$, where per each user U_x and each task i , on the sample space $\Omega_i^{U_x}$, we define Q_{ij}^x as the times the user U_x has gone from T_i to T_j (from the historical data set, step 1 of the algorithm).

As shown in equation (6), the sum of the values of the first row of $Q_{ij}^{U_1}$ is $\sum_{i=1}^4 Q_{1i} = 6$, therefore, $p_{11} = \frac{Q_{11}}{6} = \frac{1}{6} = 0.167$; $p_{12} = \frac{Q_{12}}{6} = \frac{3}{6} = 0.500$ and so on. The corresponding transition matrix P for user U_1 is then:

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} 0.16 & 0.50 & 0.33 & 0 \\ 0.33 & 0 & 0.16 & 0.50 \\ 0.20 & 0.40 & 0.20 & 0.20 \\ 0.40 & 0 & 0.40 & 0.20 \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

A new threshold δ is defined based on the values of the transition matrix P , that is, it depends on the user behaviour and the 2-task sequences performed in a session. To select it, we have taken into account that we want to eliminate the less likely sequences of tasks, i.e., with low probability of having been performed

by that user, and of course remove those whose likelihood is zero. For this reason we cannot take the minimum probability as a threshold because it would be zero in most of the cases, but the smallest one different from zero. Even more, we have set an upper limit for this threshold, the first quartile, as it will reduce false positives ($\delta \leq 0.250$).

Let us see an example. First, sorting the values of P as follows, $(0,0,0, \mathbf{0.16}, 0.16, 0.20, 0.20, 0.20, 0.20, 0.33, 0.33, 0.40, 0.40, 0.40, 0.50, 0.50)$, we obtain the threshold $\delta = 0.16$.

Assuming that $\hat{a}_{i,j} = p_{ij}$ is an estimation of $a_{i,j}$ (equation 1), we will evaluate a new working session applying this procedure. If the new session is $s_{act}^{U_1} = (T_2, T_4, T_1, T_1, T_2, T_3)$, the sequences are $-(T_2, T_4), (T_4, T_1), (T_1, T_1), (T_1, T_2), (T_2, T_3)-$, and applying the Markov probability matrix, their estimated probabilities are: $\hat{a}_{2,4} = p_{2,4} = 0.5$, $\hat{a}_{4,1} = p_{4,1} = 0.4$, $\hat{a}_{1,1} = p_{1,1} = 0.16$, $\hat{a}_{1,2} = p_{1,2} = 0.5$ and $\hat{a}_{2,3} = p_{2,3} = 0.16$. All of them are $p_{ij} \geq \delta$, thus the sequence is identified as normal and labelled as non-data leakage by the system.

Let us evaluate another new session, $(T_2, T_2, T_1, T_3, T_4)$ (see Figure 6, last row); the estimated values of the sequences are now: $\hat{a}_{2,2} = (T_2, T_2) = P_{2,2} = 0$, $\hat{a}_{2,1} = (T_2, T_1) = P_{2,1} = 0.33$, $\hat{a}_{1,3} = (T_1, T_3) = P_{1,3} = 0.33$, and $\hat{a}_{3,4} = (T_3, T_4) = P_{3,4} = 0.2$. In this case there is, at least, one sequence with probability $p_{ij} \leq \delta$ ($p_{2,2} = 0$). Thus, the binary sequence (T_2, T_2) is identified as anomaly.

Of course the results change if the threshold value varies. In the previous example, if $\delta = 0.250$ instead of 0.16, evaluating the same session $s_{act}^{U_1} = (T_2, T_2, T_1, T_3, T_4)$ (see Figure 6, last row), the estimated values are now: $\hat{a}_{2,2} = P_{2,2} = 0$, $\hat{a}_{2,1} = P_{2,1} = 0.33$, $\hat{a}_{1,3} = P_{1,3} = 0.33$, and $\hat{a}_{3,4} = P_{3,4} = 0.2$. Then, there are now two sequences with probability $p_{ij} < \delta$ ($P_{2,2} = 0$ and $P_{3,4} = 0.2$). Thus, those binary sequences (T_2, T_2) and (T_3, T_4) are identified as possible anomaly.

We carried out some experiments using $\delta = 0.250$ and compared them with the values of Table 3 ($\delta < 0.250$). The total number of false positive (FP) was 2939 for $\delta < 0.250$ and 3552 for $\delta = 0.250$. Besides, the accuracy of the classifier was much better for $\delta < 0.250$ (48.07% vs. 37.18%), and the DR also bigger (47.44% vs. 34.64%). That is, it is better to use a smaller threshold δ because it better filters the cases with low probability. This proves the correctness of the choice of the threshold in order to reduce the false alarms.

4.3.2 Anomaly detection type B

The algorithm calculates the probability of going from state T_i to state T_j in m time steps, where m is a finite number. In this case the future states depend on the past m states.

$$p_{ij}^m = Pr(T_m = x_m / T_0 = x_0, T_1 = x_1, \dots, T_{(m-1)} = x_{(m-1)}) \quad (10)$$

As an example of anomaly detection type B for a new session of user U_1 ; we compute the probability of $s_{act}^{U_1} = (T_2, T_2, T_1, T_3, T_4)$, in m steps, as shown in the following expressions. The threshold is now $\delta = 0.125$.

Step #1, $m = 1$

$$p_{T_2, T_2}^1 = P^1 = 0 < \delta \text{ then } (T_2, T_2) \text{ is probably an anomalous sequence}$$

Step #2, $m = 2$

$$p_{T_2, T_1}^2 = P^2 = 0.28 > \delta \text{ then } (T_2, T_1) \text{ is probably a normal sequence}$$

Step #3, $m = 3$

$$p_{T_1, T_3}^3 = P^3 = 0.28 > \delta \text{ then } (T_1, T_3) \text{ is probably a normal sequence}$$

Step #4, $m = 4$

$$p_{T_3, T_4}^4 = P^4 = 0.21 > \delta \text{ then } (T_3, T_4) \text{ is probably a normal sequence}$$

If any of the transitions has a probability smaller than δ , it is then classified as possible anomaly. In this case it had not been necessary to calculate the steps from $m = 2$ to $m = 4$ because for $m = 1$, $P^1 < \delta$, therefore the sequence was classified as anomalous even if the rest of the transitions are identified as normal.

Let's see another example. For a given session, $s_{act}^{U_1} = (T_2, T_4, T_1, T_1, T_2, T_3)$, $m = 5$, the probability of the transition in m steps is calculated as:

Step #1, $m = 1$

$$p_{T_2, T_4}^1 = P^1 = 0.5 > \delta \text{ then } (T_2, T_4) \text{ is probably a normal sequence.}$$

Step #2, $m = 2$

$$p_{T_4, T_1}^2 = P^2 = 0.224 > \delta \text{ then } (T_4, T_1) \text{ is probably a normal sequence.}$$

Step #3, $m = 3$

$$p_{T_1, T_1}^3 = P^3 = 0.277 > \delta \text{ then } (T_1, T_1) \text{ is probably a normal sequence.}$$

Step #4, $m = 4$

$p_{T_1, T_2}^4 = P^4 = 0.252 > \delta$ then (T_1, T_2) is probably a normal sequence.

Step #5, $m = 5$

$p_{T_2, T_3}^5 = P^5 = 0.267 > \delta$ then (T_2, T_3) is probably a normal sequence.

All the probabilities are bigger than $\delta = 0.125$, therefore this session is identified as normal and the detection process ends.

So far we have applied an anomaly detection algorithm. To do data leakage, we just check if any of the files that have been accessed during the task identified as anomalous contains confidential information. If any of the operations have been executed on files that belong to the set of critical activities, $T_c = \{T_1, T_2, \dots, T_n\}$, defined as such by an expert, then a decision should be made on whether blocked the user to protect the information. Otherwise, and in any case, the decision-making system will send an alarm to the administrator.

That is, we distinguish between:

- Normal behaviour: the sequence of operations on the computer system matches the expected one for that user.
- Anomalous behaviour: the user is performing operations that do not match with the expected profile; therefore the algorithm detects an attempted attack.
- Data leakage: the anomalous behaviour involves the access to information that has been classified as confidential or critical.

Figure 7 shows the diagram of the whole procedure that has been described.

Figure 7. Data leakage detection procedure.

4.3.3 Enhancing the results

As the system is designed to monitoring users' activities, it must avoid introducing overhead and so to be used at real time. That is why it is important to decrease the number of false alarms that slows down the work pace of the user.

However, we are dealing with probabilities, and we could be wrong when identifying a normal or an anomalous sequence. With the step of the Markov chains, the probability of a normal sequence being detected as anomaly decreases. Thus, the probability of an anomalous sequence to be identified as such increases. We are therefore increasing the reliability of the true positives.

To express it in a more formal way: our method tries to improve the quality of detection by this double-checking. The model can be formulated as follows.

Let sq_i be the i -th sequence of the set of sequences of tasks $SQ=\{sq_1, \dots, sq_n\}$ that inputs into the system. Let X_i , Y_i and Z_i be binary variables defined as,

$$X_i=1 \Leftrightarrow Sq_i \text{ is an anomalous sequence}$$

$$Y_i=1 \Leftrightarrow Sq_i \text{ is detected as an anomaly after step 2}$$

$$Z_i=1 \Leftrightarrow Sq_i \text{ is detected as an anomaly after step 3}$$

Otherwise they are zero. Then,

$$P(X_i=0/Y_i=1) \geq P(X_i=0/Z_i=1)$$

Meaning that the probability after step 2 of being wrong (detecting a normal sequence as anomaly) is greater than the probability after step 3 of being wrong. That is, the probability of false positive (FP) is reduced by introducing step 3 in the detection algorithm.

We could say that we are surer when we say that a sequence is a possible attack after applying Markov chains. Due to this, the DR index will improve after applying this last step because the number of sequences identified as normal is greater and the number of possible anomalies has decreased.

5. Results and discussion

The algorithm has been applied to the real data described in section 3.1. A number of 12.727 sessions were used, where only 512 were attacks, and the rest, 11.215, are considered normal. As it is well known, data containing authentic fraud scenarios is often not available for researchers but, on the other hand, classifiers need training data to successfully distinguish normal from fraudulent behaviour. That is why, in order to balance the sets of positive and negative examples, we have applied Negative Selection Algorithm to generate 1000 more negative samples. This is a common practice (Li, Liu, and Zhang, 2015).

We have used 5589 sessions (44%) for training and 7138 for testing (56%), including the 1512 anomalous sessions available. We will show the influence of the number of examples on the effectiveness of the decision system because if you generated more fraudulent sessions the results do not improve much and, nevertheless, the computing is more demanding.

Results are given first in terms of percentage of correctly classified (CC) and incorrectly classified (IC) sessions, using the following definitions.

- TN (true negative): normal session detected as normal
- TP (true positive): data leakage successfully detected as such
- FN (false negative): data leakage incorrectly detected as normal session
- FP (false positive): normal session incorrectly detected as data leakage.

The correctly classified CC value corresponds to the Detection Rate (DR),

$$DR = \frac{\text{No. of attacks that are correctly classified as attack (TP)}}{\text{Total No. of attacks in the test dataset (TP + FN)}}$$

The Accuracy Rate (AR), as defined by Eesa, Orman, and Brifceni, (2015), is defined as:

$$AR = \frac{\text{No. of correctly classified (TN + TP)}}{\text{Total No. of instances in the test dataset}}$$

The errors are given by the False Positive Rate (FPR) or False Alarm Rate (FAR) as defined by (Elhag, 2015).

$$FPR = \frac{\text{No. of normal that are uncorrectly classified as attack (FP)}}{\text{Total No. of normal sessions (FP + TN)}}$$

Obviously, higher values of DR and AR, and lower values of FPR show better classification performance for the data leakage detection algorithm.

The algorithm has been tested for 10 different users. First, it was evaluated applying the first steps of the algorithm, that is, without applying the Markov chains. The results are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Results of the algorithm (without Markov chain) for 10 users with dataset of Ecuador.

User	#Normal Sessions	#Fraudulent Sessions	#Total Sessions	TP	TN	FP	FN	%AR	%Error	%DR	%FPR
1	778	114	892	45	364	414	69	45.85	54.15	39.47	53.21
2	535	121	656	56	249	286	65	46.49	53.51	46.28	53.46
3	465	167	632	74	273	192	93	54.91	45.09	44.31	41.29
4	589	233	822	115	282	307	118	48.30	51.70	49.36	52.12
5	381	133	514	67	176	205	66	47.28	52.72	50.38	53.81
6	402	111	513	51	201	201	60	49.12	50.88	45.95	50.00
7	594	210	804	125	264	330	85	48.38	51.62	59.52	55.56
8	525	179	704	89	247	278	90	47.73	52.27	49.72	52.95
9	638	146	784	68	311	327	78	48.34	51.66	46.58	51.25
10	719	98	817	42	320	399	56	44.31	55.69	42.86	55.49
Total	5626	1512	7138	732	2687	2939	780				
Average								48.07	51.93	47.44	51.91

The detection rate, that is, the percentage of sequences correctly classified, is around 47,5% and the accuracy of the decision system is 48%. For some of the users it gets values up to 59,5%. However, it is still very low. We then apply Markov chains in order to improve these results and mainly to reduce the number of false positive, particularly, the FPR index. In fact, once the Markov chains are applied to double-check the decision on whether a session is normal or anomalous, the results clearly improved, as it can be seen in Table 4.

Table 4. Results of the algorithm (applying Markov chains) for 10 users with dataset of Ecuador.

User	#Normal Sessions	#Fraudulent Sessions	#Total Sessions	TP	TN	FP	FN	%AR	%Error	%DR	%FPR
1	778	114	892	78	743	35	36	92.04	7.96	68.42	4.50
2	535	121	656	96	501	34	25	91.01	8.99	79.34	6.36
3	465	167	632	104	465	0	63	90.03	9.97	62.28	0.00

4	589	233	822	203	548	41	30	91.36	8.64	87.12	6.96
5	381	133	514	106	359	22	27	90.47	9.53	79.70	5.77
6	402	111	513	88	378	24	23	90.84	9.16	79.28	5.97
7	594	210	804	181	567	27	29	93.03	6.97	86.19	4.55
8	525	179	704	142	507	18	37	92.19	7.81	79.33	3.43
9	638	146	784	116	606	32	30	92.09	7.91	79.45	5.02
10	719	98	817	67	685	34	31	92.04	7.96	68.37	4.73
	5626	1512	7138	1181	5359	267	331				
Average								91.51	8.49	76.95	4.73

The DR is now much better, 78% and the AR improves up to 91.5%, that it is indeed a good result taking into account we work with real data. The best performance of the algorithm gives AR = 93,03 % and DR = 90,03 %. Besides, the false positive rate is now quite low (FPR = 4.73%). If FPR were high, the detection algorithm would be inefficient because it would wrongly identify correct sessions as data leakage, unnecessarily blocking the access and slowing down the working pace of the users.

It is worthy to remark that the number of false positive (false alarms) has been greatly reduced from 2939 to 267. Even more, for some users we even get FPR = 0, meaning all the sessions were correctly classified. Besides, the number of attacks incorrectly detected as normal session is now 331, very low. The number of false negative is also small, meaning that the system is able of correctly detect anomalous behaviour.

We also did other experiments increasing the number of examples, i.e., generating more anomalous sessions. In Table 5 the results show the performance of the system when 4356 were anomalous sessions, most of them obtained synthetically.

Table 5. Results of the algorithm with real data (more anomalous sessions generated)

	CC%	#CC sessions	Error %	#Error sessions
Data Leak	92.47%	4198	7.53%	342
Normal	97.10%	5284	2.90%	158
Total	94.78%	9482	5.22%	500

As it is possible to see, the accuracy of the detection system is now 94,78 %, no so far from the 91,51 % when using only 1000 extra fraudulent sessions.

Admittedly, it is quite difficult to compare any detection algorithm to other procedures because there are many different types of data leakage and different approaches, depending on the objectives, the data usage, etc. Having said that, we found another real database in Aeberhard, Coomans, and de Vel (1994) where to prove our proposal. It is based on the idea that the Unix commands used by a user in a workstation define his profile. From the database, available at <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/datasets/UNIX+User+Data>, we were able to download not only the Unix commands but the sequence of commands used by each user.

The Unix command data summarizes the daily use of UNIX commands by users of a set of networked workstations. The cited paper deals with seven different users and the frequencies of use of five Unix commands in a day over 12 days. These commands are: “finger”, “man”, “who”, “date” and “more”. Besides, authors generate synthetic data using different random distributions. In their case the classification does not takes into account the sequence of commands, but the relative frequency of use. We have download sessions of commands that are concatenated by date order to then apply our algorithm. This new experiment has allowed us to compare the results of the intrusion detection algorithms that are presented in that paper and ours on the same database. Besides, this example has allowed us also to compare the efficiency of the detection algorithm in terms of computational time and to extend the potential of our proposal to other real applications.

The best classifier that is shown in that paper (Regularized Discriminant Analysis, RDA) gets 70.5% hits in the classification. In fact, among the 9 datasets used in that paper, the worst results are obtained for this Unix command database. For training, we used 500 sessions of other users as anomalous session samples. Again, we show the results without applying Markov chains (Table 6) and with this last step of the detection procedure (Table 7). We obtain a better classification of the nine users, identifying which of the users a particular sequence of operations belongs to or if it does not match any, in which case it could be a data leakage. The results were 68.84% of correctly classified sessions applying the algorithm up to step 3 and a detection rate of 96,03% with Markov chains.

Table 6. Results of the algorithm (without Markov chain) for 9 users with the Unix dataset.

Users	#Normal Sessions	#Fraudulent Sessions	Total sessions	TP	TN	FP	FN	AR	Error%	DR%	FPR%
user_0	567	500	1067	256	263	304	244	48.64	51.36	51.2	53.62
user_1	515	500	1015	275	246	269	225	51.33	48.67	55	52.23
user_2	1069	500	1569	402	821	248	98	77.95	22.05	80.4	23.2
user_3	501	500	1001	468	327	174	32	79.42	20.58	93.6	34.73
user_4	955	500	1455	314	723	232	186	71.27	28.73	62.8	24.29
user_5	582	500	1082	347	386	196	153	67.74	32.26	69.4	33.68

user_6	3419	500	3919	471	2481	938	29	75.33	24.67	94.2	27.43
user_7	1522	500	2022	417	1124	398	83	76.21	23.79	83.4	26.15
user_8	713	500	1213	329	540	173	171	71.64	28.36	65.8	24.26
Total	9843	4500	14343	Average				68.84	31.16	72.87	33.29

Table 7. Results of the algorithm (applying Markov chains) for 9 users with Unix dataset.

Users	#Normal Sessions	#Fraudulent Sessions	Total sessions	TP	TN	FP	FN	AR%	Error%	DR%	FPR%
user_0	567	500	1067	481	500	19	67	91.94	8.06	96.2	3.66
user_1	515	500	1015	484	508	16	7	97.73	2.27	96.8	3.05
user_2	1069	500	1569	478	1033	22	36	96.3	3.7	95.6	2.09
user_3	501	500	1001	490	496	10	5	98.5	1.5	98	1.98
user_4	955	500	1455	488	902	12	53	95.53	4.47	97.6	1.31
user_5	582	500	1082	485	543	15	39	95.01	4.99	97	2.69
user_6	3419	500	3919	493	3219	7	200	94.72	5.28	98.6	0.22
user_7	1522	500	2022	491	1498	9	24	98.37	1.63	98.2	0.6
user_8	713	500	1213	481	685	19	28	96.13	3.87	96.2	2.7
Total	9843	4500	14343	Average				96.03	3.97	97.13	2.03

The good result of our data leakage detection procedure on this public dataset gives us the conviction that it can also work well on other real databases, as it has been proved with the one we have presented in the paper.

5.1 Computational time considerations

The algorithm is quite efficient computationally; it takes it only between 4 to 8 milliseconds to give the result including training (Figure 8) when applied to the dataset of real access in Ecuador.

Figure 8. Algorithm performance in milliseconds with the dataset from Ecuador.

That means that our decision system can be applied on-line. In fact, each time a user begins a new activity on the computer, our system is able to analyse the sequence of operations within the current working session.

Moreover, the detection algorithm may be running at same time employees are working because they do not realize that they are being monitored. The activity of this software could be detected by the users for two reasons:

- i. Due to the fact that high overhead (processing time by monitoring) reduces the performance of the system itself and it may become unfriendly.
- ii. If this overhead is detected by fraudulent users, they can change their *modus operandis*, and therefore cheat the system.

Therefore, overhead must be controlled and have to be very small. Regarding performance it is usually accepted a 10% overhead for exhaustive monitoring and less than 0.5% for a regular case. The most classical overhead formula in performance measurement of computer systems is the ratio “execution time of the monitor software/time between two activations” (in seconds) (Huang et al., 2012).

Assuming up to 25 tasks per session, the maximum execution time of our system is 0.00112 seconds for the worst case (longest tasks). The time between two activations in an exhaustive monitoring is the accumulative time of such sequence of tasks, which can be limited by 25 times the shortest execution time of the tasks, in our case $25 \times (0.00019 + Z)$, where Z is the reflection time of the user. Then, assuming $Z = 25$ seconds (1 second per task),

$$\text{overhead} \leq \frac{0.00112}{25 \times (0.00019 + 25)} = 0.0000447$$

Therefore, the algorithm produces a maximum overhead of 0.00447 % which is very acceptable as it is lower than 0.05%. Besides, for an automated monitoring that could be set every 30 seconds (instead monitoring at event 25), the decision system gets an overhead of 0.037%, still within an acceptable range.

6. Conclusions remarks

This paper presents an algorithm for data leakage detection based on user's anomalous behaviour identification. It is structured in consecutive steps, the last one to double-check the decision on whether or not it is an attempted attack. The algorithm works with the probability of sequences of the tasks performed by a user into a computer. It has been proved efficient in terms of accuracy and with a very low false positive rate, which is one of its main advantages.

Another contribution of this paper is the representation of the users' behaviour. The codification of the tasks (operations, files) of each user has been performed defining a data structure that allows us to implement different size of sequences and sessions, i.e., it is very flexible.

Besides, after the analysis of the computational time the algorithm requires, we have drawn the conclusion that it can be used as a software monitor since it does not overhead the working time. In other words, when a user is executing a sequence of activities, the detection system monitors his activity at the same time but without slowing down the pace of work. Moreover, it can be implemented in any computer system and it is scalable.

The algorithm has been validated using real data that come from a governmental institution of Ecuador. The test results prove the good performance of this decision system for data leakage detection (94,78% DR). In addition, this algorithm was not only applied to that institutional database but it has also been applied to a public database of Unix commands with very good results (96,03%). This proves the potential of this algorithm to be applied to any other real problems as long as the data can be codified as sequences.

We think that the main limitation of our proposal is that it is a supervised algorithm, it works with historical data, and therefore we need information from the users to generate their behavioural pattern (in our case at least data of the last three months). In fact, if the sequence of tasks carried out by a user in a session is too short, the system would be not able to detect whether it is normal or not. Another limitation of our approach is that it is focused on detection and not prevention.

As future work we should be able to analyze a higher number of subsequences of tasks at the same time in order to make it quicker. Another way of improving the detection system would be to add extra information from other sources that could help to define a more complete user behavioural profile and so to enhance the reliability of the system. In a near future we would like to apply fuzzy logic in order to make a decision on blocking the system or raising an alarm, and to improve the results of the first step of the algorithm using neural networks.

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References

- Aeberhard, S., Coomans, D., & De Vel, O. (1994). Comparative analysis of statistical pattern recognition methods in high dimensional settings. *Pattern Recognition*, 27(8), 1065-1077.
- Ahmed, M., Mahmood, A. N., & Islam, M. R. (2016). A survey of anomaly detection techniques in financial domain. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 55, 278-288.
- Aziz, A. S. A., Sanaa, E. L., & Hassanien, A. E. (2016). Comparison of classification techniques applied for network intrusion detection and classification. *Journal of Applied Logic*.
- Chatziadam, P., Askoxylakis, I. G., Petroulakis, N. E., & Fragkiadakis, A. G. (2014). Early Warning Intrusion Detection System. In *Trust and Trustworthy Computing* (pp. 222-223). Springer International Publishing.
- Chari, S. N., & Cheng, P. C. (2003). BlueBox: A policy-driven, host-based intrusion detection system. *ACM Transactions on Information and System Security (TISSEC)*, 6(2), 173-200.
- Chavan, J., & Desai, P. (2013). Data Leakage Detection Using Data Allocation Strategies. *International Journal of Advances in Engineering & Technology*, 6(5), 2033.
- Cisco (2008). Data Leakage Worldwide: Common Risks and Mistakes Employees Make. http://www.cisco.com/c/en/us/solutions/collateral/enterprise-networks/data-loss-prevention/white_paper_c11-499060.html (accessed December, 2016).
- Costante, E., Vavilis, S., Etalle, S., den Hartog, J., Petkovic, M., & Zannone, N. (2013, July). Database anomalous activities detection and quantification. In: *Security and Cryptography (SECRYPT), 2013 International Conference on* (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- Eesa, A. S., Orman, Z., & Brifcani, A. M. A. (2015). A novel feature-selection approach based on the cuttlefish optimization algorithm for intrusion detection systems. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 42(5), 2670-2679.
- Elhag, S., Fernández, A., Bawakid, A., Alshomrani, S., & Herrera, F. (2015). On the combination of genetic fuzzy systems and pairwise learning for improving detection rates on Intrusion Detection Systems. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 42(1), 193-202.
- Ghorbanian, S., Fryklund, G., & Axelsson, S. (2015). Do data loss prevention systems really work?. In *Advances in Digital Forensics XI* (pp. 341-357). Springer International Publishing.

- Guevara, C., Santos, M., Martin, J. A., & Lopez, V. (2014a, May). Reaching a consensus on access detection by a decision system. In *Progress in Informatics and Computing (PIC), 2014 International Conference on* (pp. 119-122). IEEE.
- Guevara, C., Santos, M., & López, V. (2014b, August). Data Leakage Detection Algorithm Based on Sequences of Activities. In *Research in Attacks, Intrusions and Defences: 17th International Symposium, RAID 2014*, Vol. 8688, p. 477. Springer.
- Guevara, C. B., Santos, M., & Lopez, M. V. (2016a). Negative Selection and Knuth Morris Pratt Algorithm for Anomaly Detection. *IEEE Latin America Transactions*, 14(3), 1473-1479.
- Guevara, C.B., Santos, M., & López, V. (2016b) Intrusion Detection with Neural Networks Based on Knowledge Extraction by Decision Tree, *Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, 527, pp 508-517, 2016. Springer.
- Huang, X., Seyster, J., Callanan, S., Dixit, K., Grosu, R., Smolka, S. A., ... & Zadok, E. (2012). Software monitoring with controllable overhead. *International Journal on Software Tools for Technology Transfer*, 14(3), 327-347.
- Huth, C. L., Chadwick, D. W., Claycomb, W. R., & You, I. (2013). Guest editorial: A brief overview of data leakage and insider threats. *Information Systems Frontiers*, 15(1), 1.
- Kamra, A., Terzi, E., & Bertino, E. (2008). Detecting anomalous access patterns in relational databases. *The VLDB Journal*, 17(5), 1063-1077.
- Kemeny, J. G., & Snell, J. L. (1960). *Finite markov chains* (Vol. 356). Princeton, NJ: van Nostrand.
- Kim, J., & Kim, H. J. (2010, November). Design of internal information leakage detection system considering the privacy violation. In *Information and Communication Technology Convergence (ICTC), 2010 Int. Conf. on* (pp. 480-481). IEEE.
- Kumar, A., Goyal, A., Chaudhary, N. K., & Sowmya Kamath, S. (2013, April). Comparative evaluation of algorithms for effective data leakage detection. In *Information & Communication Technologies (ICT), 2013 IEEE Conference on* (pp. 177-182). IEEE.
- Lewellen, T., Moore, A. P., Cappelli, D. M., Trzeciak, R. F., Spooner, D., & Weiland, R. M. (2012). *Spotlight On: Insider Threat from Trusted Business Partners. Version 2: Updated and Revised*. Carnegie-Mellon Univ Pittsburgh PA Software Engineering Inst.
- Li, D., Liu, S., & Zhang, H. (2015). A negative selection algorithm with online adaptive learning under small samples for anomaly detection. *Neurocomputing*, 149, 515-525.
- Liao, H. J., Lin, C. H. R., Lin, Y. C., & Tung, K. Y. (2013). Intrusion detection system: A comprehensive review. *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, 36(1), 16-24.
- Liu, Z., & Lai, Y. (2009). A data mining framework for building intrusion detection models based on IPv6. In *Advances in Information Security and Assurance* (pp. 608-618). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.

- Mathew, S., Petropoulos, M., Ngo, H. Q., & Upadhyaya, S. (2010, September). A data-centric approach to insider attack detection in database systems. In *Recent advances in intrusion detection* (pp. 382-401). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- Modi, C., Patel, D., Borisaniya, B., Patel, H., Patel, A., & Rajarajan, M. (2013). A survey of intrusion detection techniques in cloud. *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, 36(1), 42-57.
- Nadeem, A., & Howarth, M. (2013). Protection of MANETs from a range of attacks using an intrusion detection and prevention system. *Telecommunication Systems*, 52(4), 2047-2058.
- Papadimitriou, P., & Garcia-Molina, H. (2011). Data leakage detection. *Knowledge and Data Engineering, IEEE Transactions on*, 23(1), 51-63.
- Sha, W., Zhu, Y., Huang, T., Qiu, M., Zhu, Y., & Zhang, Q. (2013, July). A Multi-order Markov Chain Based Scheme for Anomaly Detection. In *Computer Software and Applications Conference Workshops (COMPSACW), 2013 IEEE 37th Annual* (pp. 83-88). IEEE.
- Shabtai, A., Elovici, Y., & Rokach, L. (2012). A survey of data leakage detection and prevention solutions. *Springer Brief in Computer Science, Science & Business Media*, Springer.
- Sivakami R., Jaiganesh M, Saravanan R., (2017). An Efficient Fuzzy Self-Classifying Clustering based Framework for Cloud Security, *International Journal of Computational Intelligence Systems*, 10, 495 – 506.
- Torgo, L., & Lopes, E. (2011, June). Utility-based fraud detection. In *IJCAI Proceedings-International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence* (Vol. 22, No. 1, p. 1517).
- Vavilis, S., Egner, A., Petković, M., & Zannone, N. (2015). An anomaly analysis framework for database systems. *Computers & Security*, 53, 156-173.
- Wu, S. Y., & Yen, E. (2009). Data mining-based intrusion detectors. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 36(3), 5605-5612.
- Xu, F., Kwan, M., Tse, H., & Chow, K. P. (2014, June). A bayesian belief network for data leakage investigation. In *Proceedings of the 2nd international workshop on Security and forensics in communication systems* (pp. 19-24). ACM.
- Ye, N., & Chen, Q. (2001). An anomaly detection technique based on a chi-square statistic for detecting intrusions into information systems. *Quality and Reliability Engineering International*, 17(2), 105-112.
- Ye, N., Emran, S. M., Chen, Q., & Vilbert, S. (2002). Multivariate statistical analysis of audit trails for host-based intrusion detection. *Computers, IEEE Transactions on*, 51(7), 810-820.
- Yeung, D. Y., & Ding, Y. (2003). Host-based intrusion detection using dynamic and static behavioral models. *Pattern recognition*, 36(1), 229-243.